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Mediating Energy Resources Development and Environmental Concerns:

An Initial Step Towards the Energy Transition

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This article examines two overreaching dimensions that represent the initial step towards the energy transition in the context of oil and gas development. It is agreed that the problems facing the climate system are caused by human activity, and oil and gas production plays a particular role. Therefore, it appears important to consider the dimension related to the integration of environmental standards as the initial step of the ecological transition from the production of energy from fossil-fuel sources. This study is then based on the development of legislation in sub-Saharan African countries, which illustrate perfectly how new constraints are imposed on an activity that was originally a profit-driven activity and is now moving towards greater environmental preservation. In this sense, the first part of our article focuses on the common ground of environmental protection standards in oil and gas production. This is what we call the environmental protection standards in oil and gas production. The second part of the article analyses the reconciliation of soft law standards, which are of legal significance or the power of hard law through the legislative process, and on the liability for environmental harm in the various legislations.

I. Introduction

Energy is an essential good for human life.¹ Its role in providing most primary services is substantial.² This statement, which is true for many developing countries,³ is particularly true for sub-Saharan African countries.⁴ In the early 1960s, with the advent of independence, many sub-Saharan countries

adopted mining and petroleum laws. The purpose of these laws was to establish appropriate legal frameworks for the management and regulation of energy and natural resources. These laws were all designed to promote a profit-based national economy. In this spirit, foreign investment was encouraged and supported, with some countries turning to new international players and others to their traditional and colo-

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bures des pays d'Afrique subsaharienne, in *Droit, Humanité et Environnement: Mélanges en l'honneur de Stéphane Doumbé-Billé* 569 (A. Mekouar & M. Prieur, eds. Larcier 2020).

- 1 Aubin Nzaou-Kongo, 'The Players in the New Energy System: What Role for the State in the Anthropocene Era?' 2 *Afr. Rev. L & C. T.* 179.
- 2 World Commission on Environment and Development, *Our Common Future* (Oxford University Press 1987) 168.
- 3 Kilaparti Ramakrishna, 'The Emergence of Environmental Law in the Developing Countries: A Case Study of India' (1985) 12 *Ecol. LQ* 907.
- 4 Aubin Nzaou-Kongo, *L'exploitation des hydrocarbures et la protection de l'environnement en République du Congo. Essai sur la complexité de leurs rapports à la lumière du droit international* (University of Lyon 3 Library System 2018) 43.

nial partners.⁵ To this end, many African countries, aware of their geological potential and the economic benefits that could be directly derived from oil and gas activities, gradually supported the proclamation of a right of sovereignty over their natural resources as part of their self-determination.⁶ Over the years, the energy mix in sub-Saharan Africa, which was largely composed of fossil fuels, has also changed significantly with the integration of renewable energies.⁷ However, the major economic benefits of this mix still come substantially from oil, gas, and mining.⁸ As a result, some economies in sub-Saharan Africa rely on oil and gas for up to 80% of their export revenues.⁹ In this respect, a first paradigm shift was proposed around the 1980s to meet environmental protection needs.¹⁰ The environmental standard was enshrined in the constitution in several countries.¹¹ As a constitutional obligation, it had to be effective for the industry.¹²

Over time, the constitutional obligation was eventually deemed by some scholars to be very broad.¹³

It applied to all sectors of human activity in each country, including industrial activity and the exploitation of natural resources. Therefore, the interpretation of these provisions would require constitutional courts to uphold the rule of law.¹⁴ The perceived broad nature of environmental obligations creates an enforcement challenge for public agencies that often find it difficult to settle on the right criteria to evaluate one important factor over another. In other words, balancing the conflict that seems to exist between pursuit of business goal and environmental goals. Because of this conflict, it becomes necessary for the courts to mediate in order to interpret environmental regulations to uphold the rule of law.¹⁵ It soon became apparent that the endeavour to establish constitutional provisions¹⁶ on the environment needed to be supported by provisions in the laws applicable to each industrial sector. To this extent, a broad reform movement has been initiated in sub-Saharan Africa, aiming to insert environmental clauses into oil and gas, and mining laws. As a result,

5 Patricia Birnie, 'Environmental Protection and Development' (1995) 20 *Melb U L Rev* 66.

6 Georges Abi Saab, 'La souveraineté permanente dans les ressources naturelles,' in Mohammed Bedjaoui (ed.) *Droit international. Bilan et perspectives* (Pedone 1991) 639.

7 International Renewable Energy Agency (IRENA), *Africa's Renewable Future: The Path to Sustainable Growth* (IRENA Publication 2013) 9.

8 *Ibid* 5.

9 See Aubin Nzaou-Kongo (n 4) 25; Honore Le Leuch 'Le pétrole et le gaz naturel en Afrique' (2009) 25 *Géostratégiques* 39.

10 John R Nolon, 'Shifting Paradigms Transform Environmental and Land Use Law: The Emergence of the Law of Sustainable Development' (2012) 24 *Fordham Envtl L Rev* 242. Also, Daniel-Stefan Paraschiv, 'The Need to Intensify Measures to Protect the Environment through Legislative and Administrative Means' (2015) *JL & Admin Sci* 253.

11 For a general account of these provisions in alphabetical order: Article 27 of the Constitution of Benin of 11 December 1990: 'Everyone has the right to a healthy, satisfactory and sustainable environment and has the duty to defend it. The State shall ensure the protection of the environment.' Article 29 of the Constitution of Burkina Faso adopted by the referendum of 2 June 1991 and promulgated on 11 June 1991: 'The right to a healthy environment is recognised; the protection, defence and promotion of the environment are a duty for all.' Article 70 of the Constitution of Cape Verde of 4 September 1992: 'All citizens have the right to benefit from a healthy and ecologically balanced environment, as well as the duty to protect and conserve it (...)' Article 21 of the Fundamental Act of 4 June 1991 in Congo (RC): 'Every citizen has the right to a healthy environment which the State has the obligation to protect,' as well as Article 46 of the Constitution of Congo (RC) of 15 March 1992: 'Every citizen has the right to a healthy, satisfactory and sustainable environment and has the duty to defend it. The State shall ensure the protection and conservation of the environment.' Article 30 of the Constitution of Congo (DRC) of 09 April 1994: 'Every person has the right to a healthy

environment (...)' Article 39 of the Constitution of Madagascar of 19 August 1992: 'Every person has the duty to respect the environment; the State shall ensure its protection,' but also by extension, Article 37. Article 15 of the Constitution of Mali adopted by referendum on 12 January 1992 and promulgated on 25 February 1992: 'Every person has the right to a healthy environment. The protection and defence of the environment and the promotion of the quality of life are a duty for all and for the State.' Article 28 of the Nigerian Constitution of 26 December 1992: 'Everyone has the right to a healthy environment. The State shall ensure the protection of the environment.' Article 29 of the Interim Constitution of the Republic of South Africa of 1993: 'Every person has the right to an environment that is not detrimental to his or her health or well-being.' Article 39 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uganda of 22 September 1995: 'Every Ugandan has a right to a clean and healthy environment.' Article 47 of the Chadian Constitution adopted by the referendum of 31 March 1996 and promulgated on 14 April 1996: 'Every person has the right to a healthy environment.'

12 Karen Hulme, 'Taking Care to Protect the Environment Against Damage: a Meaningless Obligation?' (2010) 92 *Int'l Rev Red Cross* 675.

13 Maurice Kamto, *Droit de l'environnement en Afrique* (EDICEF 1996) 50.

14 W. Paul Gormley, 'The Legal Obligation of the International Community to Guarantee a Pure and Decent Environment: The Expansion of Human Rights Norms' (1990) 3 *Geo Int'l Envtl L Rev* 85; Samvel Varvastian, 'Climate Change and the Constitutional Obligation to Protect Natural Resources: The Pennsylvania Atmospheric Trust Litigation' (2017) 7 *Climate L* 209.

15 On the issue of their changing role, see George B Wyeth, 'Standard and Alternative Environmental Protection: The Changing Role of Environmental Agencies' (2006) 31 *Wm & Mary Envtl L & Pol'y Rev* 5.

16 An interesting assessment on constitutional environmental rights could be found in Joshua C. Gellers, 'Explaining the Emergence of Constitutional Environmental Rights: A Global Quantitative Analysis' (2015) 6 *J Hum Rts & Envt* 75.

a sectoral paradigm shift was considered by legislators and policy makers.¹⁷

Barely touched upon in the first generation of oil and gas laws in sub-Saharan Africa, environmental provisions were to become an essential component¹⁸ of the latest generation of oil and gas laws from the 2000s.¹⁹ Senegalese law is undoubtedly among the archetypes of this trend.²⁰ Indeed, it largely shows that environmental concerns are part of an overall movement of legal rejuvenation of energy and natural resources' law. Alongside many other new provisions, including the equitable distribution of revenues from exploitation, which is articulated around the production-sharing contract, the definition and strengthening of local content, the transparency and clarification of the tax and customs regime, the creation of a national players, the integration of environmental issues is still a timely response. But as we intend to show, this is undoubtedly a stage that must be considered to some extent as the initial stage of the energy transition. At least as to whether we should argue that the energy sector is supposed to be part of the effort. Furthermore, based on the consensus that human activity is the main cause of climate change, and that the effects resulting from industrial activity are far greater than those of everyday individuals. This implies that the social transformation brought about by the energy transition must also take place within the complex process of oil and gas production.²¹ Through this pathway, it is the option of decarbonization that is largely targeted through the technological transformation and the greening of the operational framework. For these various reasons, it

is certainly important that the energy system undergoes this deep transformation, so that it can progressively become ecologically sustainable, integrating both environmental concerns and climate change.²²

This article will focus on the legal provisions that have had a bearing on environmental transformation in sub-Saharan Africa and make the case that laws and policies will similarly play an important role in transformation of the energy sector.²³ In view of the government's desire to make the applicable standard ever more effective, it should be noted that the law will be preferred.²⁴ Thus, most of the environmental protection standards²⁵ we intend to analyse will be enshrined in legislation.²⁶ These laws will set out an obligation to protect the environment and reduce climate change effects throughout the oil and gas operating framework. They will also designate the recipient of such an obligation. We also explore primary state provisions on liability that are emerging from sub-Saharan African legislations. This depicts broadly the premises for a balanced exploitation that mediate the oil and gas production and the preservation of the environment and climate system. In this respect, we will concentrate upon legal provisions aiming to set up incentive mechanisms, such as the corporate social responsibility and local content, or rational and balanced exploitation of oil and gas. But it goes beyond that, since another set of provisions will support the principle of liability for environmental harm, as a matter of fact, we will examine the liability cause of action for ecological damage, but also the current mechanisms of remedies for environmental harm.

17 Maurice Kamto (n 13).

18 To understand the necessary reconciliation, see Patricia Birnie, 'Environmental Protection and Development' (1995) 20 *Melb U L Rev* 66.

19 See Aubin Nzaou-Kongo (n 4).

20 See Law No. 2019-03 of 1er February 2019 on the Oil Code; Law No. 2019-04 of 1er February 2019 on Local Content in the Hydrocarbons Sector. These two laws were preceded by Law No. 28-2016 of 12 November 2016 on the Hydrocarbons Code (RC), Law No. 13/2016 of 2 May 2016 Governing Oil Exploitation and Production Activities (Rwanda), Law No. 2015-035 of 16 July 2015 on the Organisation of Research, Exploitation and Transport Of Hydrocarbons (Mali), Law n° 15/012 of 1er August 2015 on the general regime of hydrocarbons (DRC), Law n° 2014/034 of 23 December 2014 on the Petroleum Code (Republic of Guinea), Law n° 11/2014 of 28 August 2014 on the Regulation of the Hydrocarbons Sector (Gabon) Law n° 07-006 of 2 May 2007 on Hydrocarbons (Chad), Law n° 8/2006 of 3 November 2006 on the Hydrocarbon Code (Republic of Equatorial Guinea), etc.

21 Aubin Nzaou, 'African Union' (2019) 30 *YB Int'l Envtl L* 539.

22 *Ibid.*

23 Th. Lauriol and E. Raynaud, *Le droit pétrolier et minier en Afrique* (LGD), 2016.

24 A comparative example of this approach can be found in this: Daniel-Stefan Paraschiv, 'The Need to Intensify Measures to Protect the Environment through Legislative and Administrative Means' (2015) *JL & Admin Sci* 253.

25 On the concept of standard, see Kimberly M. Castle & Richard L. Revesz, 'Environmental Standards, Thresholds, and the Next Battleground of Climate Change Regulations' (2019) 103 *Minn L Rev* 1349.

26 See in this sense *Schuepbach Energy LLC Case* [Prohibition of hydraulic fracking in relation to the exploration and exploitation of hydrocarbons - revocation of licences to prospect], Conseil constitutionnel français, Decision No. 2013-346 QPC of 11 October 2013, Société Schuepbach Energy LLC, JORF No. 0239 of 13 October 2013, p. 16905, text No. 20, § 18.

II. The Environmental Protection Standards in Energy Resources Development

Environmental concerns are now receiving unremitting attention in sub-Saharan Africa.²⁷ One major concern being environmental and climate harm throughout the oil and gas production process,²⁸ is now being addressed in various ways through the legal instruments. Over the past 20 years, oil and gas laws and contracts have set new standards for environmental protection,²⁹ some of which protect the climate.³⁰ They impose the general obligation to protect the environment and determine a number of addressees, while new legal and economic techniques are proposed and tend to support the implementation of the obligation to protect the environment.

1. The Overall Obligation to Protect the Environment

The integration of new environmental rules into the legislation of sub-Saharan African states has favoured the consecration of an obligation to protect the environment, also referred to as the duty to protect.³¹ There is no longer any reason to doubt the willingness and textual endeavour of African states to subject the free and open sphere of oil and gas production to new constraints. Nearly half a century later,³² it has become clear to many African legislators, often influenced by the government initiative that the time has come to articulate the duty to protect with the inherently profit-driven exploitation of hydrocarbons.³³ It is even envisaged that reconciliation will become the cornerstone of the rules governing oil and gas activities. In this respect, the shift from a thoroughly profit-driven approach to an environmentally friendly activity will allow environmental protection to move from a secondary standard to an overriding requirement. Among the cogent reasons for measuring the extent of the obligation are certainly its content and the host of its addressees.

To see what the content of such an obligation amounts to, it seems interesting to first understand its formulation in the oil and gas laws of African states. While the wording is similar in all respects, the purpose of the obligation is to protect the environment from any kind of harm from the activity,³⁴

whether industrial or accidental, and to support the implementation of all means compatible with the rational and balanced exploitation of hydrocarbons. Having been designed *ab initio* to integrate environmental standards in the oil and gas process, the obligation has over time begun to serve a cross-cutting purpose, confirmed for example by the wording of Article 213 of the RC's hydrocarbons law and Article 2 paragraph 2 of the Chadian hydrocarbons law.

An analysis of these different pieces of legislation reveals commonality in the management of environmental risks in the oil and gas process. It is primarily the responsibility of the contractor, as a key player in the process, to conduct operations in such a way as to control the environmental impact throughout the oil and gas production phases. As such, the contractor must anticipate the environmental hazards of the process by setting up a risk prevention plan that embeds corrective actions in the event of an accidental or operational environmental risk. This common ground also extends to the obligation to monitor the

27 We argue here that the deliberate approach of sub-Saharan states to establishing mandates and standards is closely related to much of the literature on environmental standards. To understand such an approach based on the emergence of environmental rules and standards. See generally Priscila Pereira de Andrade, 'The Emergence of Transnational Environmental Law' (2016) 13 Braz J Int'l L 18; Priscila Pereira de Andrade, 'O Direito Transnacional' (2016) 13 Braz J Int'l L 17; Tseming Yang & Robert V. Percival, 'The Emergence of Global Environmental Law' (2009) 36 Ecology LQ 615; Hugo Tremblay, 'The Emergence in Environmental Flow Protection in Quebec Law' (2010) 51 C de D 801; Douglas R. Weiner, 'International Environmental Policy: Emergence and Dimensions' (1985) 9 Md J Int'l L & Trade 293; Michael P. Vandenbergh, 'The Emergence of Private Environmental Governance' (2014) 44 Evtl L Rep News & Analysis 10125; Byung-Sun Cho, 'Emergence of an International Environmental Criminal Law' (2000) 19 UCLA J Evtl L & Pol'y 11; E Lynn Grayson, 'The Pollution Prevention Act of 1990: Emergence of a New Environmental Policy' (1992) 22 Evtl L Rep News & Analysis 10392.

28 See for example Colin T. Reid, Aylwin Pillai & Andrew R. Black, 'The Emergence of Environmental Concerns: Hydroelectric Schemes in Scotland' (2005) 17 J Evtl L 361.

29 Robert J. Fowler, 'International Environmental Standards for Transnational Corporations' (1995) 25 Evtl L 1.

30 Michael Livermore & Richard Revesz, 'Rethinking Health-Based Environmental Standards' (2014) 89 NYU L Rev 1184.

31 Katherine G. Horner, '"A Climate of Lawlessness": Upholding a Government's Affirmative Duty to Protect the Environment Using Deshaney's Special Relationship Exception' (2020) 29 J L & Pol'y 285.

32 H Jeffrey Leonard and David Morell, 'Emergence of Environmental Concern in Developing Countries: A Political Perspective' (1981) 17 Stan J Int'l L 281.

33 Adrian Crasnobaev, 'The Fundamental Duty to Protect the Healthy Environment' (2014) 2014 Studii Juridice Universitare 304.

34 James A Hourihan and Patricia A Brannan, 'The Emergence of Hazardous Waste Litigation' (1981) 8 Litig 25.

entire process, which implies that the operational framework is subject to particular care and monitoring. In view of the foregoing, legislators are trying to mandate schemes for detecting primary risks that may arise from the activity. As a result, the schemes aim to encourage the correction of critical risks as soon as they appear or emerge. The continuous monitoring process is carried out through a permanent assessment of the compliance of facilities, works, equipment and even instruments and products used with the standards in force. Thus, the duty to protect is usually coupled with the duty to monitor and control oil operations, which the Oil and Gas Administration will ensure.³⁵

In furtherance of this approach, two sets of considerations must be considered to comprehend the particularly high authority of the new environmental standards. These considerations will allow the duty to protect to find a notable expression according to the importance given to it by the legislations in each case. Firstly, great emphasis should be laid on the nature of the obligation, which is now an overriding mandatory provision, also known as ‘loi de police,’ in some instances.³⁶ Article 173 of Gabon’s hydrocarbons law serves as a classic illustration of both the most comprehensive way of intensifying the effects of an environmental obligation, and the type of constraints needed to deal with a profit-driven activity. On all grounds, it is appropriate to look upon the overriding mandatory provision as legislative and regulatory provisions applicable, with regard to environmental protection, in an imperative way. It seems at the outset necessary to refer, in the case of mandatory provisions, to the terms and dominant trends that emerge from Article 9 of Regulation (EC) No 593/2008 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 June 2008 on the law applicable to contractual obligations (Rome I).³⁷

35 Petroleum Act, Article 67; Guinea Petroleum Act, Article 120.

36 C. Bisping, ‘The Common European Sales Law, Consumer Protection and Overriding Mandatory Provisions in Private International Law’ *Int’l L & C Q*, Vol. 62, Issue 2, 2013, pp. 463-484.

37 Regulation (EC) No 593/2008 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 June 2008 on the law applicable to contractual obligations (Rome I) *JO L 177 du 4.7.2008*, p. 6–16.

38 J.-B. Racine, ‘Droit économique et lois de police’ (2010) 24 *Rev. Int’l D Eco* 61.

39 Michael N. Schmidt, ‘Delegation and Discretion: Structuring Environmental Law to Protect the Environment’ (2000) 16 *J Land Use & Env’tl L* 111.

40 DRC Hydrocarbons Act, Article 177.

Overriding mandatory provisions are considered as:

1. (...) provisions the respect for which is regarded as crucial by a country for safeguarding its public interests, such as its political, social or economic organization, to such an extent that they are applicable to any situation falling within their scope, irrespective of the law otherwise applicable to the contract under this Regulation.
2. Nothing in this regulation shall restrict the application of the overriding mandatory provisions of the law of the forum.
3. Effect may be given to the overriding mandatory provisions of the law of the country where the obligations arising out of the contract have to be or have been performed, in so far as those overriding mandatory provisions render the performance of the contract unlawful. In considering whether to give effect to those provisions, regard shall be had to their nature and purpose and to the consequences of their application or non-application.

Assessed in the light of circumstances, it must be said that the Gabonese oil and gas Act confers a substantive obligation to protect through the overriding mandatory provision.³⁸ This can be inferred from the fact that the environmental obligation—as stated—should not be derogated, either by convention or by legal or administrative acts. As a result, the binding force of the Hydrocarbon Code’s environmental obligation as set out will gradually take hold and influence the process, so that all stakeholders will be subject to it and can hardly derogate from its application.

The dimension that further sustains the obligation to protect is that of public interest, also known as general interest. A traditional postulate of public law that has influenced environmental law.³⁹ In this respect, Article 177 of the DRC’s Hydrocarbons Code contemplates that based on public interest, a decree deliberated in the Council of Ministers could mandate a prohibition of oil and gas operations or simply suspend a project in progress. To achieve such an outcome, it is laid out that by means of public interest, notably for reasons of national defense, security of persons, economy, or any incompatibility resulting from the exercise of the former activities and the protection of the environment, a prohibition of oil and gas operations can and should be imposed.⁴⁰ So, the government will resort to the administrative clas-

sification of the related area. Once this is done, the area is then deemed a ‘no-go zone for hydrocarbon-related activities.’

Also, it seems instructive to observe that the necessary precautionary measures will, in some cases, be applicable in the public interest. Article 12 of the Equatorial Guinea Hydrocarbons Code, for example, provides that ‘necessary precautionary measures’ must be applied in the event a serious environmental hazard. For this reason, throughout the operational framework or if a specific activity is likely to cause environmental harm, and based on national interest, administrative or regulatory measures must be taken by the government. As a result, the Ministry of Hydrocarbons shall take the necessary precautionary measures to preserve public interest.

In furtherance of the public interest, a range of provisions in RC’s Hydrocarbons law provide for a prohibition, on the basis of ‘public order’ or ‘general interest,’ of upstream operations in all available oil and gas fields.⁴¹ This is the case with Article 88, which provides the Minister in charge of hydrocarbons with the power to suspend, partially or totally, if necessary, oil operations until adequate measures are taken or if the contractor fails to respect or implement the environmental obligation.⁴² As can be seen, the analysis cannot be limited to the content of the obligation to protect, as it is also important to identify the addressees.

For the purposes of substantiating the duty to protect, the identification of the recipients of this duty is an essential element for its effective application. On this point, which takes on a particular significance with regard to the role of the various actors involved in the oil and gas process, national legislations clearly emphasize that it is the responsibility of the contractor, its associates, and subcontractors to conduct operations in strict compliance with the obligation to protect. Accordingly, the RC’s Hydrocarbons law covers all those involved in the process,⁴³ even extending this obligation to service providers, whose role may—in some cases—be fundamentally subsidiary. In this respect, Article 86 of RC’s Hydrocarbons law covers a very broad spectrum, unlike the provisions of Article 156 of the Hydrocarbon Code of the DRC, which tends to limit on the obligation to contractors and subcontractors. As a matter of fact, the difference in degree observed between these two legislations may be justified by the latitude that the legislator reserves for the judge to interpret such pro-

visions.⁴⁴ However, it seems difficult to accept such an assumption in the case of the Cameroonian, Central African, and Equatorial Guinean hydrocarbon laws,⁴⁵ which designate the holder of the mining title⁴⁶ or the state’s co-contractor⁴⁷ as the recipient of such an obligation. To all appearances, the provisions of the legislation studied do not seem to preclude the identification of the public persons involved in the operations as the addressees of this obligation. This is the case when state-owned public enterprises, constituted either as public industrial and commercial establishments or as public limited companies with public or majority share capital, carry out exploration or production activities.⁴⁸ This cannot be ruled out as regards the liability of the various participants in the oil and gas process.

With regard to the content of such an obligation, it is always necessary to assess its exact content as well as the limitations of general scope that derive from it in the national legislations, especially concerning the operational system of hydrocarbons. In order to adapt its application, national legislators have provided identical legal protection techniques in order to preserve its real scope.

2. The Implementation of the Obligation to Protect

In addition to enshrining an obligation to protect, the drafters of African national Hydrocarbons laws were inspired by the legal techniques widely accepted in environmental law. Oil and gas law commands the practical implementation of the duty to protect, based on legal and economic instruments.

When it comes to legal instruments, nearly all state laws refer to the environmental impact assessment

41 RC Hydrocarbons Act, Article 27, para. 4.

42 Aubin Nzaou, ‘Congo’ (2020) 31 YB Int’l Envtl L 259.

43 Ibid, Article 86.

44 In comparison, we find the argument developed in this article very interesting, which could be considered for African rights. Dan L. Gildor, ‘Preserving the Priceless: A Constitutional Amendment to Empower Congress to Preserve, Protect, and Promote the Environment’ (2005) 32 Ecology LQ 821.

45 Equatorial Guinean Hydrocarbons Act, Article 66.

46 Ibid, Article 82.

47 Cameroonian Hydrocarbons Act, Article 12; Central African Act, Article 56.

48 Chadian Oil Act, Article 4.

and the emergency environmental risk management plans. These instruments are intended to ensure that the obligation to protect is not limited to the inculcation of timid guidelines, but that it is translated into action throughout the oil and gas process.

The Environmental Impact Assessment is a procedural obligation incorporated in Oil and Gas Acts.⁴⁹ As its wording suggests, which is indeed found in almost identical terms in state hydrocarbon laws, environmental impact assessment is an obligation derived from the general obligation to protect. It so happens that the field of impact assessments has been extended to local content issues. In this sense, legislators will then refer to it as environmental and social impact assessment in the RC and DRC, or even further as environmental, social and cultural impact assessment in Mali.⁵⁰

As is common to many legislations, an environmental impact assessment is carried out before the entire oil and gas process is initiated. In many respects, this assessment is conducted at the site where the development is to take place and in the surrounding areas,⁵¹ whether it is for exploration or for exploitation *per se*. Thus, the contractor is required to submit an environmental assessment to the competent administrative authority. The environmental impact assessment gives special emphasis to the general obligation to protect. It is based, as a general rule, on the production of a series of documents giving an ecological state or assessment of the environment and marine biodiversity,⁵² a statement of the envi-

ronmental and social impact, but also a presentation of the project's environmental and social impact. It states further different measures envisaged to reduce,⁵³ restore or compensate for the harmful consequences of the oil operations carried out.⁵⁴ The social nature of this assessment relates to the direct or indirect impact of the operations on the hygiene, physical health of people, and the safety of their property in the areas surrounding the fields. Another aspect to be considered in relation to these legal techniques is the development and implementation of risk management plans.

The environmental risk management and contingency plan is another dimension to consider when dealing with legal instruments. To sustain the content of the obligation to protect, state legislations have added quite a natural outgrowth to the obligation to carry out an environmental impact assessment, namely the environmental risk management contingency plans. This technical device, although stated in very specific terms in most African hydrocarbon laws, is intended to promote environmental risk management. To this end, the contractor develops and implements cost plans to manage the various pollution risks identified.

Assessed in the light of circumstances, it is also possible to see that there is a common approach to risk management. On the one hand, it is necessary to adopt an environmental management plan *stricto sensu*,⁵⁵ comprising all the elements necessary for the prevention and monitoring of operational risks.⁵⁶ On the other hand, it is almost recommended to establish an emergency plan, in order to curb the occurrence of operational risks.⁵⁷ As such, and regardless of other circumstances, laws have traditionally emphasized the value of establishing abandonment, decommissioning, and rehabilitation plans for sites that, beyond the fact that they fall within the technical constraints fostered by the Oil industry, have environmental implications. Nevertheless, the RC's Hydrocarbons law contains a number of innovative aspects, such as waste management plans and atmospheric discharge management plans, which are part of a truly consolidated protective postulate, taking into account the concern for climate change in the rules applicable to hydrocarbon exploitation. The Senegalese law gives details of the assets to be protected, soil and subsoil water, flora and fauna heritage,⁵⁸ whereas the Malian law adds specific value to the cultural heritage, particularly archaeological heritage.⁵⁹

49 The reference to procedural obligation is recently made by the International Court of Justice. It has been also referred to by a set of Oil and Gas Acts. See *Certain Activities Carried Out by Nicaragua in the Border Area (Costa Rica v. Nicaragua) and Construction of a Road in Costa Rica along the San Juan River (Nicaragua v. Costa Rica)*, Judgment, I.C.J. Reports 2015, 665

50 Malian Hydrocarbons Act, Article 2, para. 51.

51 See C.E.D.R. E, *Environmental Impact Assessment: a Legal Progress?* (Proceedings of the colloquium held on 17 May 1991) (Publications Fac. Saint-Louis, 1991) 212.

52 See Michel Prieur, 'Instruments internationaux et évaluation environnementale de la biodiversité : enjeux et obstacles' (2011) 5 *Rev Jur Envtl* 7.

53 See A. Gillespie, 'Environmental Impact Assessments in International Law' (2008) 2 *Rev Eur Community & Int'l Envtl L* 221.

54 See A. Nzaou-Kongo (n 5) 294.

55 RC Hydrocarbons Act, Article 157.

56 Chadian Petroleum Act, Article 29.

57 RC Hydrocarbons Act, Article 161.

58 Senegalese Hydrocarbons Act, Article 53.

59 Senegalese Hydrocarbons Act, Article 72.

In the light of these findings, it can be concluded that, over and above the hard core that has gradually formed through legal instruments, the authority of environmental protection rules is gradually being strengthened. However, from a technical point of view, the use of economic instruments is likely to further strengthen this authority.

Economic tools are undoubtedly the other set of instruments used by legislators to implement the duty to protect, with a particular focus on special prevention funds, and insurance policies.

Special prevention funds are among economic instruments in the spotlight in many legislations. For reasons related to the nature of the accidents on many offshore platforms or operational fields, the use of special damage prevention funds appeared to be the appropriate means. These special prevention funds, which are financial mechanisms constituted by annual allocations made by the contractors or holders of mining titles, have become a major economic instrument. Their purpose is to manage the effects of oil activities on the environment,⁶⁰ risk prevention,⁶¹ rehabilitation,⁶² and site abandonment.⁶³ As a result, these funds help constitute a financial provision that can be used in the event of a pollution incident, or any event covered by the purpose of the fund. In addition to the special funds, the guarantee against the risk of damage also includes the framework of damage risk insurance.

The obligation to take out insurance policies has gained momentum in subsequent legislations in African states as another financial scheme to cover operational risks in the oil & gas sector. The contractor is obliged to take out insurance against all risks of environmental accidents, spills, pollution, waste, and any other damage to the ecosystem, biodiversity, or human health.⁶⁴ In the RC, this obligation extends beyond the contractor, as the legislator considers that subcontractors and service providers cannot be exempted.⁶⁵ Compulsory insurance is a fundamental condition for the granting of a mining title under Article 90 of the RC's Oil and Gas law, and is subject to verification of the operator's financial capacity. It goes without saying that this obligation applies to almost all oil and gas activities. In conjunction with such an obligation, the obligation of transparency on revenues and profit deriving from oil and gas activities is now enshrined in many laws, including Senegal,⁶⁶ Guinea,⁶⁷ and Côte d'Ivoire.⁶⁸ This obligation is imposed on both the mining title hold-

er and the state companies to optimize oil revenues and control oil costs.

As can be seen, the new legal and economic aspects of environmental protection are supported by a range of different instruments, including environmental and social impact assessment, emergency and protection plans, special funds, insurance and even more transparency obligations. The development of observed standards demonstrates the emergence of a common ground on the duty to protect the environment in sub-Saharan Africa oil and gas activities. This paves the way for new specific approaches which reveal complementary aspects of protection. Without any doubt, the new standards promote a paradigm shift from a profit-driven business to a balanced activity with a focus on the revenues needed for sub-Saharan economies and for sustaining life on earth.

III. The Premises of a Sustainable Energy Resources Development

Oil and gas legislation in sub-Saharan Africa has also devised—notwithstanding legal and economic techniques—soft law mechanisms for environmental and climate protection. These mechanisms intend to resolve the dilemma between oil and gas production and environmental protection by overwhelmingly favouring the former. As the oil and gas industry has historically been a profit-driven area, it was inherently difficult to reverse this dominant reality. Therefore, the challenge for legislators has been very broad. They have to set different legal parameters that would foster a rational and balanced exploitation of natural resources, within the framework of sustainable development, by supporting a rapid widening of the constraints imposed on exploitation. Therefore, the social responsibility of oil companies,

60 Chadian Hydrocarbons Act, Article 65.

61 RC Hydrocarbons Act, Article 98.

62 Gabonese Hydrocarbons Act, Articles 197 and 198.

63 Equatorial Guinean, Article 114.

64 Chadian Hydrocarbons Act, Article 61.

65 RC Hydrocarbons Act, Article 90.

66 Senegalese Hydrocarbons Act, Article 55.

67 Guinea Hydrocarbons Act, Articles 114 and 115.

68 Cote d'Ivoire Act, Article 82.

the local social content and the civil and/or criminal responsibility of companies in the event of environmental harm caused by them, as well as the modalities for repairing this harm, will be established as mechanisms.

1. Incentive Mechanisms

The use of incentive mechanisms is the first aspect of pursuing balanced exploitation. As an illustration of the virtuous dynamic that can easily be associated with these legislative efforts, incentive mechanisms constitute one of the substrates of balanced exploitation of hydrocarbons. Three of them reveal the importance that the law now gives them: corporate social responsibility, local content and rational and balanced exploitation of hydrocarbons.

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) is one of the features incorporated into oil and gas legislation. The mechanism is unique in that it allows sub-Saharan oil laws to reconcile the three pillars of sustainable development: economic performance, social responsibility, and protection of the environment.⁶⁹ In Gabon, CSR is now the central core of the legislation, from which companies are required to ‘contribute to the challenges of sustainable development, to improving the well-being of local populations and to protecting the environment.’⁷⁰ The objectives of such an approach are twofold. On the one hand, CSR should encourage financial support for the investments needed to diversify the national economy, particularly through the Provision for Diversified Investment (PID). On the other hand, the scheme should generate the capital that will allow the development of the oil and gas industry itself, by means of the Provision for Investment in Hydrocarbons (PIH).⁷¹ In Senegal, this CSR appears only incidentally. In this regard, Article 5 of the Senegalese Petroleum law on

‘the ownership of resources and the management of oil revenues’ makes a subtle shift towards CSR when it specifies the objective of oil revenue management. Firstly, it is aimed to meet the need for the development of the national economy, notably through the ‘promotion of public investments’ in sectors with growth potential. Secondly, to ‘guarantee intergenerational savings.’⁷² In RC, CSR is anchored in mechanisms for promoting studies and research by the contractor, its subcontractors, and service providers, allowing ‘the improvement of hygiene, health, safety and environmental protection conditions.’ Provided for in Article 87 of the RC’s Hydrocarbons law, the CSR scheme, the contours of which are in appearance difficult to define, undoubtedly foreshadows the considering of local content.

Another incentive also illustrates the way in which legislation encourages oil and gas players to integrate environmental and social concerns into their activities. Local content is intended to be the very driver of environmental and social issues in oil and gas projects. In both RC and Gabon, local content refers to activities aimed at ‘the development of local capacities, the use of local human and material resources, the training and development of local skills, the transfer of technology, the use of local goods and services, and the creation of additional measurable value to the local economy.’⁷³ In Senegal, the local content Act in the hydrocarbons sector provides that ‘local content in the hydrocarbons sector refers to all initiatives taken to promote the use of national goods and services and the development of the participation of national labor, technology and capital in the entire value chain of the oil and gas industry.’ The Senegalese Petroleum law sets out in Article 58 local content obligations, employment obligations, professional training, and technology transfer, which focuses on social issues but can also be applied to the environment. This is the case when local content requirements add value by supporting the deployment of renewable energies.⁷⁴ By promoting technology transfer in PV solar or wind energy, this scheme can give a boost to the environmental and climate effort provided that it does not discourage foreign investors.⁷⁵

The scheme is still expressed with some finesse in Equatorial Guinea. The state, as well as contractors, is obligated to contribute ‘to the study, design, construction, equipment, operation and maintenance of the Technological Institute of Hydrocarbons of Equa-

69 See World Commission on Environment and Development (n 3) 211.

70 Gabonese Hydrocarbons Act, Article 190.

71 Gabonese Hydrocarbons Act, Article 191.

72 Senegalese Hydrocarbons Act, Article 5.

73 RC Hydrocarbons Act, Article 3.

74 OECD (2015), *Overcoming Barriers to International Investment in Clean Energy, Green Finance and Investment*, OECD Publishing, Paris, <https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264227064-en>.

75 Ibid.

torial Guinea and to the creation of training centres for people from Equatorial Guinea working in oil operations.⁷⁶ Similarly, it is incumbent on the government to take the necessary measures to create a national fund to encourage the participation of citizens in oil operations. In this regard, individuals are entitled to a right of preference in their dealing with contractors for the supply of goods, services, human resources, and capital.⁷⁷ A similar clause exists in Guinea.⁷⁸

In DRC, local content is financed by contributions and provision for social interventions. Indeed, the contractor is required to ‘contribute annually to the training of state employees in the hydrocarbons sector, to social interventions ... to the operation of the oil and gas data bank.’ Mali provides for a community development plan required of the contractor who must finance social programmes, while Côte d’Ivoire requires the oil title holder to finance the training programme for its Ivorian staff as well as that of ‘agents of the Ivorian oil administration, of all qualifications.’⁷⁹

In addition to the incentive mechanisms observed, balanced hydrocarbon management also incorporates elements of rational and optimal exploitation.

Finally, with regard to the incentive schemes, the rational and balanced exploitation is another aspect that should be taken into consideration. The need for optimal and rational use of hydrocarbon deposits is also part of the body of measures aimed at improving the technical and social conditions related to oil and gas production. As a result of the reconciliation of environmental and economic ends, this dimension has firmly acquired a particular importance. In RC, by virtue of Article 81 of the Hydrocarbons law, the optimal and rational use of hydrocarbon deposits has a major interest, that of preserving the ecological balance of the marine environment which, as a result of the conduct of operations, undergoes substantial impacts in the exploited areas. The environment is threatened insofar as it constitutes a habitat for marine biodiversity. Consequently, the contractor’s technical and financial capacities must be mobilized to encourage rational and optimal use of resources. In doing so, the contractor must be as diligent as possible in delineating the deposit and carrying out the exploitation operational work.⁸⁰ In DRC, characteristic of the prohibition of exploration and exploitation operations in certain marine areas, the requirement for rational and balanced exploitation has led

to the creation of marine protected areas,⁸¹ hence the prescription: ‘The exercise of hydrocarbon activities upstream is prohibited in protected areas and prohibited zones.’ This is a protection of public interest based on the need to preserve certain species of fauna or flora, whose extinction could be caused by industrial activity.

Since the last movement to reform oil and gas laws in Africa, the facts lead to the integration of the true scope of the ban on gas flaring associated with oil extraction as an element of optimal and rational use of resources. The ban on gas flaring, which first appeared in the early 1990s, has been given greater perspective and appreciation, appropriately, by the international climate change initiative, Zero Routine Flaring. In Equatorial Guinea, Article 76 of the Hydrocarbons Code provides that ‘It is strictly forbidden for the Contractor and/or its Associates to flare any quantity of natural gas in the context of petroleum operations.’⁸² While technical, economic, and financial reasons have long been put forward to justify such a ban, environmental concerns are now tending to replace them. In RC, the legislator considers that the ban can only be lifted, with regard to minimum quantities and thresholds previously indicated, if a written report setting out the technical and environmental reasons submitted by the contractor is assessed and approved by the Minister in charge of hydrocarbons.⁸³ In DRC as in Chad, the legislator does not prohibit gas flaring based on environmental motives.⁸⁴ It provides the very purpose of natural gas in the hydrocarbon process.⁸⁵ Therefore, gas must be conserved for reuse, including commercial,⁸⁶ reinjection or industrial uses.⁸⁷ Of course, it is in the light of these various elements, which are not exhaustive, that the content of what represents balanced ex-

76 Equatorial Guinean Act, Article 88.

77 Equatorial Guinean Act, Article 90.

78 Guinean Act, Article 54.

79 Cote d’Ivoire Act, Article 53.

80 RC Hydrocarbons Act, Article 25 para. 2.

81 DRC Hydrocarbons Act, Article 155.

82 Rwandan Hydrocarbons Act, Article 31.

83 RC Hydrocarbons Act, Articles 136 and 137; Equatorial Guinean Act, Article 76.

84 Chadian Hydrocarbons Act, Article 99.

85 DRC Hydrocarbons Act, Articles 174 and 175.

86 Chadian Hydrocarbons Act, Articles 99 and 100.

87 *Ibid.*, Article 174.

exploitation of hydrocarbons must be considered. But the laws we are talking about have also put in place mechanisms of liability for ecological damage.

2. Liability for Environmental Harm

Environmental risk prevention is based on cost plans and insurance policies, which is the economic dimension of protection discussed in the first part of this article. Operational accidents also occur, causing serious environmental and other damage with often disastrous consequences for ecosystems, biodiversity, and human health. Where such damage occurs in an oil production system where legal constraints exist, sub-Saharan legislators now consider that environmental damage, whatever its origin, is a cause of liability and must be remedied.

It is worth starting with the liability as a cause of action for ecological harm. Certain specificities emerge from the rules applicable to the compensation of ecological damage. For what can be considered as significant innovations, the analysis of the provisions on environmental liability now leads to not relativizing the true scope of the diversity of the forms of liability retained by the legislators of sub-Saharan Africa states.

The legislations of the DRC and Cameroon refer to strict liability. In Cameroon, Article 62, paragraph 1, provides that ‘Without prejudice to the penalties applicable in criminal matters, the Holder of an Authorization or a Petroleum Contract who, through his own actions or those of his subcontractors, has caused personal injury, material damage or environmental damage directly or indirectly related to the exercise of petroleum operations, related activities or installations located inside or outside the contractual perimeter (...)’ is civilly liable, without the need to

prove fault. The same considerations govern the liability regime established by the DRC’s legislator. Article 156 specifies that ‘The contractor or his subcontractor is required to respect the legal and regulatory provisions relating to the protection of the environment and cultural heritage. He is objectively responsible for any damage caused in the context of hydrocarbon activities.’

It goes without saying that there can be no misunderstanding the scope of these provisions, which clearly present the bundle of responsibilities that these two legislations choose to retain. No doubt, for various reasons, and particularly the difficulties involved in establishing evidence in the case of operational pollution, this solution seemed to be the most appropriate in all respects. In so doing, it is considered that there is an endeavour to objectify civil liability in order to obtain compensation for ecological damage more easily. So, objectified civil liability means that it is worth retaining ecological damage, due to the exploitation of hydrocarbons, by detaching it from personal injury, namely bodily harm, as a fully-fledged basis for liability. It also reflects one of the underlying tenets of the polluter pays principle, which aims to ensure enterprises internalise environmental externalities and avoid the subsidy of these costs by national regulators.⁸⁸

It should be noted that the various considerations that emerge from other legislation all relate—for the most part—to liability for faults. In RC, Article 89 provides that the contractor, its subcontractors and service providers are subject to the obligation to ‘repair damage to persons, property and the environment’ resulting from their activities. The Gabonese and Chadian legislators in turn use similar terms, although in a less prolific manner.⁸⁹ However, in Equatorial Guinea, article 67 of the law is not sufficiently precise to consider that it makes the contractor or entrepreneur liable for any damage to persons or the environment.⁹⁰

The conclusion that seems to emerge from these considerations on liability is that in the majority of sub-Saharan African legislations, ecological harm is, by its very nature, progressively becoming a cause of liability, whether objective or subjective.⁹¹ Consequently, the liability provides the individual with a means of contending any environmental harm resulting from offshore or onshore activity as well as against personal injury caused by these activities. As a result, the modes of reparation of this ecological

88 Joel P Trachtman, *The Economic Structure of International Law* (Harvard University Press 2008) 6; Edwin Mills, ‘Economic incentives in air pollution control,’ in D.A.L. Auld (ed.) *Economic Thinking and Pollution Problems* (University of Toronto Press 1972) 68.

89 Gabonese Hydrocarbons Act, Article 22; Chadian Hydrocarbons Act, Article 62.

90 Equatorial Guinea Hydrocarbons Act, Article 67.

91 Benjamin Boumakani & Aubin Nzaou-Kongo, Les nouveaux aspects de la protection de l’environnement dans les codes des hydrocarbures des pays d’Afrique subsaharienne, in Michel Prieur & Ali Mekouar (eds) *Droit, Humanité et Environnement: Melanges en l’honneur de Stéphane Doumbe-Bille* (Larcier 2020) 569.

damage in these different legislations make it possible to highlight some specificities.

Secondly, the method of reparation of ecological harm remains another major aspect linked to the contractor's liability. We note the specificities that emerge with regard to liability and the forms of reparation chosen. In RC, Article 203, according to which 'Anyone who, through negligence, imprudence or failure to comply with the relevant regulations, commits or attempts to commit acts contrary to the protection of ... the environment, as provided for in this law and its implementing texts, shall be punished by a prison sentence of between three months and five years and a fine of between fifty million (50,000,000) to one billion (1,000,000,000) CFA francs, or one of these two penalties only' is likely to clarify the interpretation of the provisions applicable to the obligation to remedy ecological harm.

This provision lays the new foundations for the dual civil and criminal liability that results, when the facts are acquired in a dispute, from the existence and ascertainment of ecological damage.⁹² There are two important aspects to this. On the one hand, the absence of the necessary diligence or the occurrence of environmental damage exposes the contractor to double liability. On the other hand, according to the terms of Article 204, failure to comply with the obligation to carry out an environmental and social impact assessment also makes the contractor liable to the same penalties. Such firmness on the part of the RC legislator is unparalleled. In Cameroon, the provisions of Article 62 also provide for double liability. However, the legislator does not provide any details regarding the criminal sanctions incurred or the amount of compensation to be paid for ecological harm. Moreover, although the same provision emphasizes the interest of replacing or restoring the damage⁹³ as an alternative to compensation, the legislator does not specify the content of the reparation in kind that is deduced from it either.

Apart from these two situations, compensation is essentially asserted as a method of reparation for ecological harm. This is generally the case in Senegal, which provides for 'compensation for damage and harm resulting from oil operations and caused [by the oil title holder] and/or companies working on its behalf.'⁹⁴ This is also the case in DRC, where Article 156 also refers to compensation. None of its provisions applying to pecuniary reparations, particularly as provided for in Articles 183 to 185 of the oil and

gas law, make any reference to environmental requirements. Similarly, the strict or extensive reading of the provisions providing for criminal sanctions in articles 186 to 188 of the law does not allow for such a possibility. As for Equatorial Guinea, Article 67 of the oil and gas law emphasizes, without any other plausible development, the obligation to compensate for ecological harm. The same is *a fortiori* true for Chad, given the provisions of Article 62 of the law. In Gabon, on the other hand, Article 22 of the law, although it provides for compensation for environmental damage, does not specify the nature of the damage. There is a reason to believe, however, that it is compensation in kind, because this vagueness of the law is coupled with the specificity of recourse to the transaction to settle disputes related to ecological damage. In any case, this specificity raises questions about the conditions for assessing ecological damage in the context of a settlement. As this is the joint or concurrent responsibility of the oil and gas administration or the navy, should it be treated as an expert opinion, or should it refer to any expertise in the field? This is certainly a question that arises somehow.

IV. Conclusion

The enshrinement of a general obligation to protect the environment, as well as the legal and economic techniques that constitute its avatars, are particularly significant for boosting the paradigm shift towards a decarbonized activity. This effort has provided the different actors involved, the State, private companies, NGOs and individuals, with new means of action for environmental protection. The States now have instruments that provide for direct control of activities and can sanction violations of environmental standards. Private companies, although they are mainly targeted by these standards, will be able to use voluntary initiatives to further green their activities and provide reports that give an effective status

92 Ilona Gorgenyi, 'Protection of the Environment through Criminal Law considering the European Standards' (2018) 13 J Agric Envtl L 46.

93 Different players are now pushing for the restoration approach. Jeanette Jensen & Alex Gardner, 'A Legal Obligation to Restore Wetlands by Environment Water Allocations' (2017) 1 CJEL 158.

94 Senegal Hydrocarbons Act, Article 57.

of their efforts. All of this will be done under the watchful eye of NGOs and individuals who can always alert the authorities in charge or file petitions to activate the accountability mechanisms. It is certain, however, that the courts will have a very specific role to play when various problems may arise in the future, including enforcement gaps.⁹⁵ They will be able to address both the issues of clarity of established standards that may be challenged by oil and gas companies and explain the mandates of the administration in terms of the oversight they will be required to exercise.

In the meantime, it is possible to measure with hindsight the definite and growing influence of environmental concerns in the operational framework of hydrocarbons, reflecting the existence of a common ground, the new common legal standards in sub-Saharan Africa. These standards are the result of the reconciliation of soft law and hard law norms. They allow a real balance between the application of strict legislative rules, especially with liability rules for damages, and the freedom of action that can be granted to the oil sector to support the environmental and climate effort through voluntary initiatives. This approach, which is innovative in all respects, now seems to be widely applied. It allows the exploitation of hydrocarbons to be open to considerations whose scope

now goes beyond various contingencies, strictly economic in nature, whose importance and interest have traditionally been attested to by the economic needs of sub-Saharan countries. That is, whether economic development based on strategic resources is a problem of sovereignty, now the protection of the environment in the context of these activities is also a fact of sovereignty.⁹⁶ All these aspects will certainly strengthen the law on climate change which feeds on a variety of elements from environmental, energy and natural resources law.⁹⁷

This effort, long overdue, must be contextualized. In addition to the trajectory of the mediation which can now be historically traced, it is important to point out that this effort allows sub-Saharan Africa to be on a sustainable path of ecological transition.⁹⁸ This is an important point since other efforts are already being made in other sectors, and the oil and gas industry cannot be left out of the climate global effort. These are advances that should be seen as such, but again industry and states have a considerable role to play in this social transformation. This represents a challenge for African states, which must always achieve a constant mediation between their need for economic development, their participation in the ecological transition and their consideration of the concrete problems of social justice that concern Africans in the first place.⁹⁹ It is important to put this into perspective, because to truly support an ecological transition as such, it is important to integrate oil and gas production into the more global context of national energy policies. It is indeed in this framework that oil and gas, in competition with other energy sources, will be able to support the national mix and contribute to solving the problems of access to energy or that of the energy burden that kills many people in hospitals or clinics on the continent. A burden that only disadvantaged groups pay for. It is indeed within such a framework that the dependence of sub-Saharan African countries on oil and gas export earnings can be addressed with a little more will. The ecological transition will only make sense if alternative development paths are found.¹⁰⁰ One cannot underestimate the role of daily practice and agreements that are helping to foster, implement and provide some effectiveness¹⁰¹ to environmental standards.¹⁰²

95 See, <<https://sdg.iisd.org/news/environmental-laws-impeded-by-lack-of-enforcement-first-ever-global-assessment-finds/>> accessed 15 2022.

96 Elisa Ruozi, 'The Obligation Not to Pollute: From Corollary of State Sovereignty to the Right to a Decent Environment' (2010) 8 *Indonesian J Int'l L* 82.

97 As an emerging discipline, climate law draws on many fields of law. Jacqueline Peel, 'Climate Change Law: The Emergence of a New Legal Discipline' (2008) 32 *Melb U L Rev* 922.

98 See for instance John R Nolon, 'Shifting Paradigms Transform Environmental and Land Use Law: The Emergence of the Law of Sustainable Development' (2012) 24 *Fordham Envtl L Rev* 242; Kenneth F. McCallion & H. Rajan Sharma, 'Environmental Justice without Borders: The Need for an International Court of the Environment to Protect Fundamental Environmental Rights' (2000) 32 *Geo Wash J Int'l L & Econ* 351.

99 Aubin Nzaou-Kongo (n 1).

100 Jack B. Weinstein, 'Why Protect the Environment for Others' (2003) 77 *St John's L Rev* 217.

101 David M. Beatty, 'Polluting the Law to Protect the Environment' (1998) 9 *Const F* 55.

102 Andrea Ross & Jeremy Rowan-Robinson, 'Behind Closed Doors: The Use of Agreements in the UK to Protect the Environment' (1999) 1 *Envtl L Rev* 82.